

Land Surface Temperature and NDVI as indicators of Urban Heat Island. Case study: Different cities in Greece

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Abstract: Urban areas emerge as dynamic, constantly evolving systems, directly linked to the climate crisis and environmental changes. The issue of urban resilience is one of the 17 Goals for Sustainable Development, as stated by the UN. It is inextricably linked to trapped urban heat, the impacts on the urban environment, the economic costs and their overall management. This aforementioned phenomenon is described as Urban Heat Island and has a significant effect on the microclimate of cities. The goal of this research is to study on a space-temporal basis the intensity of this phenomenon in Greek cities and its evolution, using and programming in a modern remote sensing platform, the Google Earth Engine, combining statistical methods of prediction in external analysis software.

1. Introduction

The rise in atmospheric temperature, in conjunction with surface temperature, plays a crucial role in the climate crisis (Mustafa et al., 2020). Since the second half of the 20th century, rapid urbanization, combined with technological advancements, human well-being and a general population increase has become directly associated with economic development and urban sustainability (Filho et al., 2017). The intensification of this phenomenon arguably posed one of the most decisive challenges of the 21st century at a global level, as it led to dramatic alterations in land cover in order to address economic urban development and residents' needs (Rimal et al., 2018).

Urban Heat Island (UHI) is intricately linked to both human activities within urban areas as well as productive endeavors. This phenomenon has been studied across abroad geographic coverage (Kim and Brown, 2021). Its existence became noticeable during the 19th century, a period when major urban centers in northern Europe began to take shape.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1 Study Area

The current study is performed in the Region of Thessaly in Greece and especially for the most populous Municipalities. The selection of them is based on the population according to the 2021 census records (Table 1).

Fig. 1. Location map of the selected study areas

Larissa has a population of 164,095 making it the first most populous city in the Region. Municipality of Larissa plays a major role as the center of the Region. It is considered as an economic and commercial center with a rapid urbanization, over the last two decades. On the other hand, Municipality of Volos has a different topology due to immediate vicinity with Pagasetic Gulf and Pelion mountain. Volos' location makes it an important port and tourist destination all year round. The Municipalities of Trikala and Karditsa have a significant geographic position and developed urban centers with commercial, cultural, and tourist activities.

Table 1. Population in Region of Thessaly according to the 2021 census records

Region of Thessaly	
Municipalities	Population (2021)
Larissa	164,095
Volos	136,670
Trikala	78,605
Karditsa	55,979

Data Source: Hellenic Statistical Authority (ELSTAT)

2.2 Datasets/Databases

The aim of this paper is to analyze and visualize Landsat Surface Temperature (LST) timeseries taken from Landsat-8 and Landsat-9 sensors, over specific defined areas of interest (AOI) in Thessaly region, specifically in the most populous Municipalities. The research is performed using Landsat 8 and 9 images from Collection 2, over the period between 2013 and 2020. Landsat Collection 2 satellite data were used, considering that they have already been corrected radiometrically, geometrically and atmospherically. The data used are atmospherically corrected in order to avoid surface reflectance, so that Landsat spectral Band 10 is converted into a thermal band.

Subsequently, mean daytime and nighttime Land Surface Temperature (LST), across the chosen date and year range, were calculated, using MODIS - Terra Satellite images with the spatial resolution of 300 m.. For the distinction of areas in urban and peri-urban ones, the CORINE Land Cover was used as a background, containing areas categorized into urban and peri-urban classes. The main codes for this distinction are those in Level-1 in CORINE Land cover and characterized as urban and build-up land.

2.3 GEE: Cloud Based Platform

Google Earth Engine (GEE) was launched in 2010 by Google LLC and is based on the companys' computational infrastructure, as well as the available open-access satellite data. It is the most popular platform for geospatial data processing, with a wide variety of applications (Gorelick et al., 2017), including monitoring vegetation (Zhang et al., 2019), forest ecosystems (Shimizu et al., 2019; Wei et al., 2020), agricultural crops, land cover change (Derdouri et al., 2021; Midekisa et al.,

2017), climate change impacts through the “Climate Engine”¹ platform, urban environments (Duan et al., 2019; Ranagalage et al., 2019), hydrological cycles (X. Li et al., 2022), coastal fronts (Sagawa et al., 2019), and natural disasters (Kakooui & Baleghi, 2020; Meilianda et al., 2019; Uddin et al., 2019). The key advantage is that users perform data analysis through the web application and there is no need to download the data (Gorelick et al., 2017). Additionally, another online web app, “Collect Earth”², was developed for assessing changes in land cover, as a result of collaboration between Google, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), NASA, and the U.S. Department of Agriculture (Saah et al., 2019). Also, Google LLC has launched the “Climate Engine” platform and “SpatiaFi”³ online environment, in order to combine geospatial and economic data, for observing the way global changes and economic actions are linked.

2.4 Methodology

The loaded satellite data for the region of interest, issued from Landsat-8 and Landsat-9 sensors in the GEE platform, have undergone preprocessing, atmospheric correction, and orthorectification. A specific function has been created, in order to mask clouds and cloud shadows, based on the “QA_PIXEL” band of Landsat-8 and Landsat-9 sensors. Another function was created to transform surface temperature digital maps (ST), in Celsius degrees maps, using Landsat scale factors.

Fig. 2. Scheme of the adopted methodology for calculating timeseries of land surface temperature

Changes in land surface temperature, during the daytime and nighttime affect immediately the intensity of urban heat island. The intensity of the UHI is a good numerical indicator to measure how a city affects the local climate, in comparison to its rural environment. This indicator is affected by a lot of factors, such as the heat issued by the human activities, the buildings, the existence of urban green areas and the total energy consumption. The maximum values of urban heat island tend to be observed during nighttime, due to the fact that the heat is trapped by the cities and that the heat is retained during the day (Y. Li et al., 2020; Martin-Vide et al., 2015).

To calculate the intensity of urban heat island, we calculated the mean value for the entire Feature Collection (the whole set of satellite images) that we have created for urban and peri urban areas during daytime and nighttime. SUHI intensity is measured by subtracting the mean urban temperature from the mean rural temperature for day and night.

$$SUHI_{nighttime} = (LST_{mean} [Urban/Night]) / (LST_{mean} [Rural/Night])$$

$$SUHI_{daytime} = (LST_{mean} [Urban/Day]) / (LST_{mean} [Rural/Day])$$

The primary issue in estimating SUHI is the lack of a well-defined approach, for identifying urban and surrounding reference areas. The absence of a clear and consistent definition between different kinds of urban areas in the literature, makes it exceptionally difficult to make meaningful comparisons of SUHI values. In this study, the specific categorization of code 112 in the CORINE Land Cover digital maps may be associated with peri-urban areas, which are transitional zones between urban and rural environments. These regions typically encompass a range of land uses, including sparsely populated residential areas, commercial districts, various infrastructure and they tend to have a lower population density compared to the central urban areas (Sobrino & Irakulis, 2020).

¹ <https://app.climateengine.com/climateEngine>

² <https://app.collect.earth/>

³ <https://climateengine.com/introducing-spatiafi/>

3. Results

3.1 Analysis of land surface temperature timeseries

The following Charts show Landsat Surface Temperature Series for the aforementioned Municipalities of Thessaly Region. The x-axis represents the years ranging from 2013 to 2022 and the y-axis represents surface temperature in Celsius degrees. Temperatures in observed Municipalities are ranging from 34 to 48 degrees. In the Municipality of Trikala there is not an obvious trend line (Figure 3), but there are specific minimums, that seems to go down around 34° C, during July 2017 and 2019. In the Municipality of Volos (Figure 4), as well as in Municipality of Larissa (Figure 5), there is an infimum during July 2017. In the Municipality of Karditsa (Figure 6), special minimums in land surface temperature are observed during July 2016 and 2020.

Fig. 3. Landsat Surface Temperature Time Series in Municipality of Trikala

Fig. 4. Landsat Surface Temperature Time Series in Municipality of Volos

Fig. 5. Landsat Surface Temperature Time Series in Municipality of Larissa

Fig. 6. Landsat Surface Temperature Time Series in Municipality of Karditsa

3.2 SUHI intensity

Table 2 shows, that the UHI Variations in the UHI intensity ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) during 2013 and 2022, exhibits the mean day-time and night-time UHI.

Table 2. SUHI Intensity for study areas

SUHI Intensity	
Municipalities	Values
Larissa	1.164
Volos	-0.668
Trikala	1.322
Karditsa	0.548

SUHI intensity in the Municipality of Volos reach to -0.7 during daytime and night-time. This result shows that urban areas are cooler during the day than the surrounding rural areas and it could be justified by the orthocanonical urban planning system in the city of Volos and environmental factors such as the green areas, that are located in many places inside the town (Sobrinho & Irakulis, 2020). Municipalities of Trikala, Larissa and Karditsa present approximately the same values of SUHI intensity. According to SUHI intensity in these regions, there is a moderate increase in temperature within the urban area, compared to its rural surroundings, which is a common characteristic of urban heat islands.

4. Conclusion

Extensive development throughout urban areas has led to unprecedented urbanization, causing a remarkable transformation of their landscapes. The findings of this research can be supported to assess the effects of UHI intensity in Greek cities in future studies. Also, they can serve as valuable information for promoting sustainable urban planning in these cities. In the future evolution of this research, there will be an attempt to analyze the temperature dynamics of UHI (Urban Heat Island) with corresponding satellite-derived indices, such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI).

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